

Coupling Factor Determination in the Control of Unintentionally Generated RF Fields

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Abstract: Radiated emissions and susceptibility requirements imposed in bands where intentional RF reception or transmission does not occur is problematical. It is often desired to compare radiated emissions with radiated susceptibility performance to assess system level compatibility. For reasons purely theoretical and because of practical measurement limitations, this is not realistic. McCollum and Clark[1] proposed a limit and test method that provided a direct comparison of radiated emissions and radiated susceptibility performance in those cases where only unintentional emissions and reception are of interest (non-tunable electronics). This test method, referred to as bulk current emissions (BCE) testing, and its associated limit is a complimentary test method to bulk current injection testing and radiated susceptibility testing. Previous work utilized victim and culprit circuits with low common-mode loop impedance. Forward work identified in this publication was to determine how different loop impedance on culprit and victim circuits affected cable-to-cable coupling and the corresponding BCE test limit. Cable coupling factors for victim and culprit circuits with different loop impedance are investigated.

INTRODUCTION

Background

McCollum and Clark[1] proposed a new test method to replace or supplement low frequency radiated emissions testing in frequency bands where intentional receivers are not utilized. The new method, referred to as bulk current emissions testing, is complimentary to the bulk current injection, or CS114, testing of MIL-STD-461D[2]. McCollum and Clark identified forward work required to understand the cable coupling process and how to apply the limit and test method. The previous work was based on coupling between shielded cables; cables with low common mode loop impedance. Cable coupling factors for high loop impedance and mis-matched loop impedance are presented herein.

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Rationale for Test Method and Limit

NASA scientific payloads and equipment often contain circuits and sensors in which the voltages being measured or transmitted are on the order of 10 – 100 microvolts. In order to glean any information from these small signals, it is extremely important to protect against crosstalk. However, there is no current military or NASA crosstalk limit or test method. Although a complete system functional test may determine whether crosstalk is a problem, complete testing is not always possible, as shown by the failure of the Wake Shield Experiment during the STS-60 Space Shuttle Mission [3]. Also, discovery of such problems is best made prior to hardware integration. Imposition of this test method would allow such problems to be found during equipment-level or subsystem-level testing.

DEVELOPMENTAL TESTS AND RESULTS

Test Setup

Figure 1 is a schematic of the cable coupling factor test setup. Cable bundles consisting of a single twisted pair approximately 2 meters in length were placed on 5 cm non-conductive standoffs. The cables were connected through an isolated chassis-mount BNC connector to a resistor circuit card at each end. By moving jumpers on the circuit card, the resistance from line-to-ground on each line could be set to either 330 or 4700 Ohms. The cables were tested at a 5 cm separation configuration and adjacent configuration. Two configurations involved having a braided shield placed over one of the twisted pairs and grounded at each end through a 7.5 cm pigtail. In one shielded configuration, the victim was shielded and the culprit was referenced to ground through 4700 ohms at each end. The other shielded configuration involved having the culprit shielded and the victim referenced through 4700 ohms. Using a network analyzer and a bulk current injection (BCI) probe, a signal was impressed onto the culprit cable bundle. The injected current (reference port) and the current coupled onto the victim bundle (test port) were measured by the network analyzer using identical current probes and compared. The test measurement divided by the reference measurement is the cable coupling factor.

Coupling Factor Testing

In order to determine the cable coupling factor (ratio of current coupled to victim to culprit current), a signal was injected into the BCI probe using the source port of the network analyzer as the signal generator. The culprit current was monitored using a current probe connected to the reference port and the victim current probe (identical to the culprit current probe) connected to the test port. The ratio of the test port voltage to the reference port voltage yielded the coupling factor. Measurements were taken with the cable bundles separated by 5 cm and with the bundles adjacent to each other. In addition to the shielded configuration previously mentioned, the victim was referenced to ground through 330 ohms at each end and coupling factor measured with the culprit referenced through both 330 ohms and 4700 ohms. The victim was then referenced through 4700 ohms at

each end and the measurements repeated with the culprit in each of the two different configurations. The frequency range of test was between 10 kHz and 30 MHz. Above 30 MHz, cable resonance made measurements difficult and repeatability nearly impossible.

Results

Figure 2 shows the results of the coupling factor testing in which the cabling was adjacent. As can be seen from the figure, the cable coupling factors are well below 0 dB until the frequency approaches 30 MHz. The exception is the case where the culprit is of high impedance and the victim is shielded. Even in this case the coupling factor is roughly -5 dB over most of the frequency band.

Figure 1. Cable Coupling Test Setup

Figure 2. Cable Coupling Data for Adjacent Configurations

CONCLUSION

Earlier tests used to support the BCE limit had utilized circuits with low loop impedance. That test data supported the use of BCE for protecting against coupling between shielded cabling. Testing for this publication supports the notion that BCE testing can be used to protect against crosstalk no matter what the victim or culprit loop impedance.

As originally proposed, the bulk current emissions limit would have covered the frequency range of 10 kHz to 100 MHz. Because of the difficulty encountered and lack of repeatability, it is suggested that the limit end at 30 MHz. This will allow testing of cables lengths normally found in an equipment qualification test (1 - 2 meters). This test could eliminate or supplement the radiated emissions testing below 30 MHz, the frequency band of the active rod antenna. This test will also be complimentary to CS114. The complimentary test methods will aid analytical integration of equipment in cases where integrated functional testing is not feasible.

REFERENCES

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